

HOW IMPORTANT IT IS TO USE ONLINE RESOURCES WHEN TEACHING ENGLISH IN SCHOOL

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Abstract. *The issues of communication, interaction, authenticity of communication, language learning in cultural contexts, educational autonomy, and humanism are currently given top emphasis. By following these guidelines, culture can develop competence as a part of communication competence. The ultimate objective of teaching foreign languages is to impart the freedom to navigate in a foreign language environment and the capacity to react appropriately in various circumstances. This article offers perspectives and recommendations on the value of internet resources for classroom English language instruction.*

Keywords: *English, education, students, Internet and electronic resources, standards of instruction, and methods.*

НАСКОЛЬКО ВАЖНО ИСПОЛЬЗОВАТЬ ОНЛАЙН-РЕСУРСЫ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ В ШКОЛЕ

Аннотация. *Вопросам общения, взаимодействия, аутентичности общения, изучения языка в культурном контексте, образовательной автономии и гуманизма в настоящее время уделяется первостепенное внимание. Следуя этим рекомендациям, культура может развивать компетентность как часть коммуникативной компетенции. Конечная цель обучения иностранным языкам – привить свободу ориентироваться в иноязычной среде и способность адекватно реагировать в различных обстоятельствах. В этой статье предлагаются точки зрения и рекомендации относительно ценности интернет-ресурсов для обучения английскому языку в классе.*

Ключевые слова: *английский язык, образование, студенты, Интернет и электронные ресурсы, стандарты обучения, методики.*

INTRODUCTION

Modern approaches that make advantage of online resources are in opposition to the teaching of conventional foreign languages. To teach communication in a foreign language, you must set up actual, everyday scenarios that encourage the study of the subject matter and foster appropriate behavior (that is, the authenticity of communication is called principal). The Internet in particular is a new technology that aims to address this mistake. A communicative approach is a method that mimics dialogue and aims to create a psychological and linguistic foundation for communication by intentionally analyzing the content and ways to interact with it.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Students can use a communicative strategy on the Internet with little difficulty. The communicative assignment should invite students to discuss a dilemma or query; they should be encouraged to share knowledge as well as to assess it. Because students independently select language units for the development of their own thinking, this technique can be separated from other forms of instructional activities. The usage of the Internet is strongly encouraged in the communicative approach since it serves to pique students' interest in learning a foreign language by enhancing and adding to their existing knowledge and experience.

Creating interaction in the lesson, also known as interactivity in the approach, is one of the key needs for teaching foreign languages using Internet resources. "The combination, coordination, and filling of communicative goal and outcome efforts with the aid of speech tools" is what is meant by interaction. The Internet aids in the development of speaking abilities and skills through authentic language instruction. It also offers a sincere interest in teaching vocabulary and grammar, leading to efficiency. Interactivity pushes students to respond appropriately to real-world events in a foreign language while also simulating them.

The project method is one of the technologies that offers instruction that is focused on the needs of the individual student as a means of fostering independence, creativity, and mental activity. The projects' typology is varied. Initiatives can be categorized as single, group, spoken, written, online, and concrete projects. In actual fact, dealing with mixed projects containing research projects, creative, practical, and educational elements is frequently important. Reading, listening, speaking, and grammar are all covered in the project work language's multidimensional learning approach. The project method encourages group study projects and actively supports students' development of independent thought.

RESULTS

I believe that collaborative skills are taught to students through project-based learning, which also shapes students' creativity and moral qualities like empathy and mutual aid. There is generally no distinction between teaching and learning when a project is being taught. The project method involves the development of students' communication skills, treatment culture, ability to form ideas clearly and quickly, ability to tolerate the opinions of communication partners, ability to obtain information from a variety of sources, processing using modern computer technologies, and creation of a language environment that supports the emergence of a natural need.

Foreign language proficiency is currently a requirement for receiving a trade degree. There is a substantial need for learning because experts from a wide range of industries frequently engage with international partners. In today's culture, learning foreign languages is becoming a more crucial component of job training. People first acquire such knowledge at schools, colleges, and lyceums, and later in establishments, training programs, or by being familiar with the fundamental knowledge sets that enable them to independently learn a foreign language. For those with varied levels of language skill, there is a vast array of instructional tools available today. The sage strategies and abilities of teachers are essential to the achievement of this objective.

DISCUSSION

The ability to integrate information technology and contemporary teaching techniques helps students pick up new information quickly. A instructor can finish some courses by fusing different approaches. Teachers and students gained knowledge about contemporary methods for teaching foreign languages in this regard. You'll be able to choose the approach that will help you reach your goals as a result. Using a variety of teaching and learning styles can still result in effectiveness. Teaching takes place in little chunks and is predicated on the student's prior knowledge foundation. Pronunciation is the focus at this point. According to Harmer, pronunciation is the primary requirement for a natural speaker.

At the upper level, independent work—particularly in foreign languages—plays a significant role. Of course, there are different requirements for this course than there are for prior

ones. Additionally, since the lesson no longer emphasizes spoken communication, a large portion of the linguistic material is currently absorbed passively (receptively). Reading comprehension is crucial, in other words. Additionally, texts are very long, and language materials are challenging to comprehend. Exercises in reading, speaking, and listening are conducted frequently. Three days are set out while organizing a lesson: one for reading, one for speaking, and one for listening. Additionally, homework is more challenging than in earlier stages. A topic and a two-minute presentation are the main components of speaking lessons. Text cards will also be offered to students as an alternative. Each student writes a response to the topic on the card of their choice. The speech requires the use of introductory words, new words, synonyms, and phrases that have already been heard. By researching new text themes online, in the media, and in the press, homework can be used to prepare them. Inspiring scientific research and discoveries will pique students' interests. The demand for learning a foreign language is rising gradually and regularly.

The four parts of a foreign language—reading, reading comprehension, listening comprehension, and speaking—each offer certain ideas and abilities. The employment of educational technology in the educational process makes it a potent tool of contemporary information technology. By introducing cutting-edge technologies into the educational process, it will also try to improve the quality and effectiveness of instruction. Using such information and communication technology, especially when learning other languages, has several benefits.

In comparison to the first stage, grammar is taught in greater depth in the middle stage, and students receive exercises and assessments based on grammar topics. Applications for learning on computers and mobile devices are also great for K–12 education. Examples include Talk (practice speaking English), Daily English, Learn English (become an English expert), and how to speak authentic English. All components of reading, listening, and testing are included in these applications. Recording new words on a phone voice recorder is another fantastic way to focus during your free time. Another efficient method of teaching the language is by displaying more cartoons and subtitles in the language.

It should be assumed that the game serves primarily as a teaching tool. The teacher exploits the students' desire to participate in enjoyable lessons and compete for prizes to further their education. The student likes to think he is proficient in speaking, listening, playing, understanding, and writing English. We are all aware that students must be treated as subjects in today's educational system. The efficacy of instruction will be increased by emphasizing more participatory methods. The ability for students to think independently is one of the most important requirements for English classes.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the goal of modern language education is to create a more cultured person who is able to assess and organize new information. The system as a whole must be updated using creative methods. With this in mind, educators can familiarize themselves with cutting-edge techniques, which they can then combine and implement in their work to significantly improve the educational system. By embracing multimedia capabilities for communication and information receipt, many firms are pushing the envelope. The use of computers and other technology determines how well the overall educational process goes.

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